

Supplementary Materials: The following are available online at www.mdpi.com/xxx/s1, Table S1. Preliminary screening for insect-resistance using non-heat-treated artificial diet supplemented with lyophilised leaf powder from 11 accessions of *C. scarabaeoides* and *C. cajan* received from Australian Grains Genebank, Figure S1. Average larval weight of *H. armigera* fed on different accessions of *C. scarabaeoides* and *C. cajan* using non-heated (green bars) and heated (red bars) artificial diet supplemented with lyophilised leaf powder, Table S2. Nutritional composition of raw mature seeds, Table S3. Summary of protein abundance for cysteine proteinase inhibitor and Lectin-domain containing receptor kinase A4.2 in *Cajanus cajan* (ICPL 87) and *Cajanus scarabaeoides* (IBS 3471) leaves.

Supplementary Table S1. Preliminary screening for insect-resistance using non-heat-treated artificial diet supplemented with lyophilised leaf powder from 11 accessions of *C. scarabaeoides* and *C. cajan* received from Australian Grains Genebank. The mean larval weight (mg) is an average of 75 replication. Values with similar letters do not differ significantly at $P < 0.05$ (Tukey's HSD test).

Genotype ID	Average weight (mg)	Country of origin	Scientific name
ICPL 87 ¹	472.4 ^A	ICRISAT/India	<i>Cajanus cajan</i>
IBS 2653	440.6 ^{AB}	Australia	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>
IBS 3481	436.5 ^{AB}	India	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>
IBS 3108	435.7 ^{AB}	India	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>
IBS 3422	417.6 ^{AB}	India	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>
IBS 3338	414.5 ^{AB}	India	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>
IBS 3155	413.8 ^{AB}	India	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>
IBS 2984	413.8 ^{AB}	Australia	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>
CRR-T-17 ²	412.3 ^B	Indonesia	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>
IBS 3277 ²	399.1 ^B	India	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>
M3002 ²	384.7 ^B	India	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>
IBS 3471 ²	322.05 ^C	India	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>

¹: susceptible to *H. armigera*

²: Top 4 accessions with moderate to high level of resistance to *H. armigera* (based on this preliminary study)

Supplementary Figure S1. Average larval weight of *H. armigera* fed on different accessions of *C. scarabaeoides* and *C. cajan* using non-heated (green bars) and heated (red bars) artificial diet supplemented with lyophilised leaf powder. A and B) Larval weight (mg) on day three and five respectively, C) Percentage of pupa formed by Day 11, D) Representative larvae fed on non-heat-treated artificial diet (D1) and larvae fed on heat-treated artificial diet (D2), both pictures were taken on day five. * Indicates significantly different at $P < 0.05$ (Tukey's HSD test) to ICPL 87 and PAD heat and non-heat diets. All data are means \pm standard errors ($n = 64$).

Supplementary Table S2. Mineral and protein composition of raw mature pigeonpea seeds. Nutrient values are per 100 g of the used portion of the dried weight and all values reported were averages of three determinations. The mineral analysis was determined using Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-EOS) as per Wheal and Palmer [55], protocol. The approximate protein content was calculated by using the estimated nitrogen value obtained by Dumas method using a TruMac® Series CNS Analyser (LECO® Corporation, USA) protein analyser as per Skylas et al. [56] protocol and multiplying it with the standard nitrogen-to-protein conversion factor of 6.25 (Jones' factors). Values with similar letters do not differ significantly at $P < 0.05$ (Tukey's HSD test).

Genotype ID	Ca	S	Mg	K	Na	P	Zn	B	Cu	Fe	Mn	Average Protein content
ICPL 87	102.06 ^E	169.06 ^D	99.96 ^E	1474.40 ^A	1.88 ^C	375.80 ^A	3.60 ^A	1.85 ^B	0.51 ^A	3.94 ^C	1.98 ^D	25.53 ^A
CRR-T-17	329.29 ^C	213.36 ^B	149.95 ^A	1308.14 ^C	1.78 ^C	324.73 ^C	3.23 ^C	1.91 ^B	1.13 ^A	4.38 ^A	3.79 ^B	22.46 ^A
M3002	426.90 ^B	216.01 ^B	119.73 ^B	1281.91 ^D	2.47 ^B	297.35 ^D	3.56 ^A	2.16 ^A	0.61 ^A	4.18 ^B	5.18 ^A	23.19 ^A
IBS 3277	312.60 ^D	206.72 ^C	106.81 ^D	1444.26 ^B	1.56 ^D	349.02 ^B	3.40 ^B	2.20 ^A	0.70 ^A	4.20 ^{A, B}	3.51 ^C	23.68 ^A
IBS 3471	450.48 ^A	236.029 ^A	113.90 ^C	1438.25 ^B	3.57 ^A	312.64 ^C	3.12 ^C	1.76 ^B	0.73 ^A	3.41 ^D	3.73 ^B	24.15 ^A
USDA [57]	130		183	1392	17		2.76		1.06	5.23	1.79	
Oshodi et al. [58]	81.4		110	1308	9.9		4.1		1.3	13.7	1.3	
Holland et al. [59]	140		100	1390	38		2.5		1.2	3.4	1.1	
Saxena et al. [60]	120.8		122				2.3		1.3	3.9		

Supplementary Table S3. Summary of protein abundance for cysteine proteinase inhibitor and Lectin-domain containing receptor kinase A4.2 in *Cajanus cajan* (ICPL 87) and *Cajanus scarabaeoides* (IBS 3471) leaves.

Uniport ID		A0A151QZF6	A0A151QZM0		
Genotype ID	Replication	Cysteine proteinase inhibitor	Lectin-domain containing receptor kinase A4.2	TMT reagent labelling of peptide	Growth stage
ICPL 87	Rep 1	612.65	38.359	129N	Vegetative stage
ICPL 87	Rep 2	623.909	49.48	129C	
ICPL 87	Rep 1	726	40.3	130N	Flowering and Podding stage
ICPL 87	Rep 2	622.974	43.089	130C	
ICPL 87	Rep 3	540.35	42.254	131	
IBS 3471	Rep 1	3524.086	159.846	126	Vegetative stage
IBS 3471	Rep 2	2790.445	172.671	127N	
IBS 3471	Rep 1	2174.961	124.48	127C	Flowering and Podding stage
IBS 3471	Rep 2	1300.956	140.613	128N	
IBS 3471	Rep 3	1148.025	162.613	128C	